

Semiconductor to metallic transition of Ba₂BiFeSe₅ under external pressure

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Abstract:

Low-dimensional transition metal chalcogenides have attracted much attention in material science, solid state chemistry, and crystal engineering. This is because these compounds are the potential targets to explore the interesting physical properties caused by the quantum many-body effects [1] and potential applications, including thermoelectrical [2] nonlinear optical (NLO) [3] electronic phenomena, and unusual magnetic properties [4]. In particular, one-dimensional Heisenberg antiferromagnetic (1D HAF) chain compounds have still been a hot topic. Since Haldane's theoretical prediction, which was made in 1983 [5]. Here, the structure of Ba₂BiFeSe₅ is built from distorted FeSe₄ tetrahedra and BiSe₅ quadrangular pyramids, which are connected to each other in an alternating fashion to generate the infinitely corrugated quasi-1D [FeBiSe₅]_n anionic ladders. It exhibits a paramagnetic (PM) to canted antiferromagnetic (C-AFM) transition achieved by means of competing super-exchange interactions [10]. The temperature dependence of resistivity $\rho(T)$ demonstrates the semiconducting property of this sample. The suppression of semiconducting behavior and its lead to induced metallic nature with application pressure up to 12 GPa. The low temperature resistivity curve suppresses and induced metallic nature is observed from the activation energy E_a was estimated to be 0.168 eV by the Arrhenius equation, $\rho(T)=\rho_0\exp^{(E_a/kBT)}$, The observed activation energy (E_a) is 0.168 eV (0 GPa) to 0.006 eV (12.3 GPa). The strong suppression of the semiconducting behavior in Ba₂BiFeSe₅ suggests that the Fermi surface is in the vicinity of some instability. It is plausible that the Fermi level is located near the edge of the conduction band. This indicates that induced superconductivity is realized in the complex Fermi surface including the impurity band with a low carrier density and a low density of states, and it rather provides benefit for achieving a higher T_c with application of higher pressure.

Reference:

1. J. S. Miller, Extended Linear Chain Compounds; Plenum: New York, 1982; Vols. 1–3.
2. K. F. Hsu et al., J. Am. Chem. Soc., 124 (11), 2410 (2002).
3. S. L. Nguyen et al., Inorg. Chem. 49 (20), 9098 (2010).
4. A. I. Baranov et al., Inorg. Chem. 42 (21), 6667 (2003).
5. F. D. Haldane et al., Phys. Rev. Lett. 50, 1153 (1983).
1. X. Li et al., Chem. Asian J. 11, 3436 (2016).